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Research Article

Intersectionality of Race, Class, and Gender: A Study of Suzan-Lori Parks' *Venus*

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ABSTRACT

People of colour face oppression in all areas of human experience. However, social scientists and literary critics often treat the various categories of oppression as mutually exclusive experiences. Such single-axis analysis of oppression misunderstands or ignores the experiences of whole groups, particularly those of women of colour. The paper aims to analyse the interlocking oppressions of race, class, and gender in the lives of marginalised people of colour, and to analyse *Venus* (1996), a play by Suzan-Lori Parks, through the theoretical framework of Intersectionality. The paper employs a qualitative, interdisciplinary method that combines Feminist theory, Black Feminism, and Critical Race Theory in literary analysis. The key findings establish that an intersectional approach to the study of the lives of women of colour contributes to an in-depth analysis of the interlocking oppressions in terms of sexism, scientific racism, colonial dynamics of imperialism, and also calls for a need for a resurrection of History.

KEYWORDS: Intersectionality, Suzan-Lori Parks, Black Feminism, Scientific Racism

FULL PAPER

Introduction

The life of Black people is constituted of many elements of inequality and oppression. Disparities across categories such as race, class, gender, sexuality, and nationality abound in measures across all areas of life, including education, occupation, income, wealth, health, hygiene, and housing. Research in the social sciences has focused on analyzing inequality by segregating these categories and treating them as independent factors that sometimes overlap under certain conditions. For instance, studies on race often focus upon “contrasting Whites with Blacks and other racially identifiable groups without taking into account historical modes of incorporation of each group. Historical linkages and systematic interrelationships that reveal the underlying ways another shapes any one dimension of inequality are rarely fully examined” (Dill 1). As a result of this approach, the experiences of whole groups, particularly those of women of colour, are misunderstood or ignored. Black women are constantly located in the intersectional oppression of race, class, and gender. The trauma of slavery has continued into the twenty-first century in various ways, and the violent forms of racism, classism, and sexism have taken the form of more subtle and indirect forms of prejudice from the late twentieth century. Black women’s race does not gain them class mobilisation, or any respect as women; their class does not offer them social prestige, dignity as women, or recognition based on race. Their condition as women places them in the bottommost position in the racial and economic order, and they receive the least pay in the job market.

Suzan-Lori Parks (1963-) is a contemporary writer, dramatist, novelist, screenwriter, and actor. Her plays have restructured the traditional notions of drama prevalent in the American theatre. She is the first African American playwright to win the Pulitzer Prize for Drama, and one of the only four African American women playwrights to have a play produced on Broadway. Parks expresses much awareness about the triple jeopardy that oppresses Black women in their lives in America. She writes plays that critique various forms of oppression and the different domains of power that create oppressive situations for the Black woman. This paper aims to analyse, through the theoretical lens of intersectionality, Parks’ *Venus* to trace the elements of oppression that interlock in the lives of her protagonist, and the various domains of power that make her oppressions possible. The paper employs a qualitative analysis of the social and cultural order prevalent in America, with reference to the intersectional oppression of Black women.

Methodology

The paper employs a qualitative, interdisciplinary method that combines Feminist Theory, Black Feminism, and Critical Race Theory in literary analysis. It

discusses the play *Venus* through the intersectional framework of analysis of oppression that emerged in the field of Critical Race Theory, as developed by Kimberle Crenshaw and later adopted by Black Feminist theories such as Patricia Hill Collins, Angela Davis, and others. It analyses the postmodern style of Suzan-Lori Parks, exploring the intersectional oppression of race, class, and gender brought forth by colonialism, organised sexism, and scientific racism in the lives of the protagonist, a woman of colour.

Theoretical Framework

Intersectionality is a field of analysis that critiques disparities based on race, class, gender, sexuality, age, physical ability, nationality, etc., to contest and interrogate existing approaches to these structures of inequality. It challenges traditional modes of knowledge production in America. It provides “an alternative model that combines advocacy, analysis, theorizing, and pedagogy – basic components essential to the production of knowledge as well as the pursuit of social justice and equality” (Dill 1). The theory focusing on the intersections of race, class, gender, and other categories of identity, as an approach to the study of inequality, has been developed and applied in interdisciplinary fields such as ethnic studies, women’s studies, cultural studies, labour studies, critical legal studies, and American studies.

Intersectional studies analyze the experiences of groups “that occupy multiple social locations and find approaches and ideas that focus on the complexity rather than the singularity of human experience” (Dill 2). It challenges traditional boundaries between disciplines and the departmentalization of ideas. It also re-examines old issues in new ways and identifies new ways of viewing humanity and social life. Intersectional studies aim to reframe the world of ideas, bringing together various ways in which human life is experienced, and use this knowledge to create a world in which all voices are heard, thereby seeking to introduce public policies that benefit all these voices. Intersectionality had its origins in the works of African American women scholars who used it as a tool to explain their own lives and to interrogate the exclusion of their experiences from both White, Eurocentric, middle-class models of feminism and the male-dominated field of Ethnic Studies. Maria Miller Stewart spoke of both structural and individual racism, as well as structural and individual sexism. Elizabeth Martinez addressed the issue of multiple oppressions, demanding simultaneous ontological roles for all. Anna Julia Cooper’s *A Voice from the South* (1892) presented a standpoint for American Black women: “The colored woman of ... is confronted by both a woman question and a race problem, and is as yet an unacknowledged factor in both” (134).

Angie-Marie Hancock states that identifying the oppressor is more complex than a single-category analysis can handle. The capitalist economic system was left

unquestioned by the White abolitionists and women's rights movement. The former worked to bring an end to slavery, and the latter struggled to eliminate male supremacy. However, neither group comprehended the systematic link among the enslavement of Blacks in the South, the exploitation of workers in the North, and the social oppression of women. It was Angelina Grimke who proposed a theory and practice that advocated an alliance of the analysis of issues of race, class, and gender in the struggle for the emancipation of Black women.

Much of the groundwork for intersectionality was laid first in ethnic studies and women's studies, as these two disciplines have always focused on issues of race, class, gender, *etc.* As intersectionality developed, innovative thinking from other fields influenced one another, thereby widening the intellectual and practical scope of intersectional approaches to understanding personal identity and the social lives of various groups of human beings. Intersectionality developed across various fields concerned with social justice and equality, such as Civil Rights and women's rights. It is not just an emergence based on a series of theoretical propositions, but a work that emerged from an attempt to improve the quality of life in society. It attempts to comprehend the lives of marginalized groups. It interrogates the obstacles and demands that arise within the various structures that play a prominent role in their lives.

Kimberle Crenshaw coined the term Intersectionality in 1989, and the concept spread beyond America, in the field of Gender Studies. Crenshaw's work in Critical Legal Studies is only a launching point, and it is not the only place where intersectionality began. Crenshaw explains Intersectionality through an analogy of traffic in an intersection:

Discrimination, like traffic through an intersection, may flow in one direction, and it may flow in another. If an accident happens in an intersection, it can be caused by cars traveling from any number of directions and, sometimes, from all of them. Similarly, if a Black woman is harmed because she is in the intersection, her injury could result from sex discrimination or race discrimination (149).

Crenshaw develops the metaphor of intersections further when she states that her objective was to "illustrate that many of the experiences Black women face are not subsumed within the traditional boundaries of race or gender discrimination as these boundaries are currently understood, and that the intersection of racism and sexism factors into Black women's lives in ways that cannot be captured wholly by looking at the race or gender dimensions of those experiences separately" (1244).

Crenshaw acknowledges that the idea of intersectionality is neither new nor her invention. She stresses that drawing attention to erasures, and to the ways that "women

of color are invisible in plain sight," has been the project of Black feminism since its inception. Though Intersectionality is a relatively new concept, "notwithstanding the term's relatively short history, it does have a long past which is closely related to Black women's fight for equality, human rights, and recognition. Formerly discussed as the 'gender, race, and class nexus', intersectionality has several forerunners and founding narratives" (Lutz 2). Intersectional scholars trace elements of intersectionality in Sojourner Truth's speech at the Akron, Ohio, Convention in 1851. The 1977 manifesto of the Combahee River Collective, a Boston-based Black Lesbian Feminist Group, spelled out its intersectional objectives.

These ideas were followed and elaborated in the works of Black feminist scholars such as Patricia Hill Collins and Angela Davis. Collins' *Black Feminist Thought* emphasizes the need to redefine what counts as intellectual in order to recover the suppressed voices of women of colour in the United States. These voices, when heard, disturbed and unsettled the hegemonic systems of racism, sexism, and classism. Davis' *Women, Race and Class* emphasised the significance of class as an important category of analysis that interacts with race and gender in perpetuating the inequality of Black women.

Intersectional Analysis of *Venus*

Many scholars consider Park's *Venus* a historical play; it deals with the life and death of the nineteenth-century Khoisan woman Sarah (Saartjie) Baartman, whose stage name was the Hottentot Venus. Baartman, born in 1789 in the Eastern Cape of South Africa, had a condition called Steatopygia; she had extremely protuberant buttocks due to the build-up of fat. She was exhibited as a freak in London, the English provinces, and Paris during the early nineteenth century. She died in 1815 in Paris at the age of 26, and her corpse was dissected by Georges Cuvier, the Baron Docteur in the play, who attempted to establish that the Hottentots were a subhuman race. Deborah Geis writes that Parks' nonlinear, multi-layered narrative and her choral, "circus like construction of the play implicate the audience in a voyeuristic fascination with the anatomy of the Venus Hottentot; they suggest the relationships among the exploitation of Saartjie, the history of colonialism, and contemporary white appropriations of black culture, or what bell hooks calls 'eating the other'" (181). The play critiques the "historical mistreatment of black bodies" (Kolin 12).

Venus consists of an Overture and 31 scenes. The scenes are numbered in reverse order, and footnotes are presented as historical extracts, including autopsy reports, descriptions of the Hottentot, definitions of terms, newspaper reports, and passages from books. The inclusion of these accounts treats fictionalized dramatic narratives and real historical excerpts as contesting accounts: "neither one is completely true or completely false" (Geis 80).

The Negro Resurrectionist announces “Footnote#1: a Historical Extract. Category: Theatrical” that is presented as: “The year was 1810. On one end of the town, in somewhat shabby circumstances, a young woman, a native of the dark continent, bares her bottom. At the same time but in a different place, on the other end of the town, in fact, we witness a very different performance” (24). Venus’ sexuality is presented in crude terms, whereas the happenings in the intertext, a play within a play called *For the Love of Venus*, deal with the story of a young White lady trying to allure a young White male. The play within a play uses elegant language to describe the heroine’s suffering, whose lover has lost interest in her because he is enamoured of the Venus Hottentot.

Venus begins with the Venus Hottentot, a young Black woman with a big posterior, presented on stage, facing stage right, showing the audience her profile. She revolves 270 degrees and faces upstage, revealing her posterior. Then she revolves another 90 degrees and faces stage right, again exposing her profile and the enormous bottom to the audience. The very first scene of the play brings onstage Venus, catering to her audience’s voyeuristic needs. All the characters announce the death of Venus, and Venus herself declares that she is dead. The Man’s Brother, later the Mother Showman, later the Grade-School Chum says, “Venus, ... sinned or else/ completely unknowing of r godfearin ways stood/ totally naked in her iron cage” (5). The historical strategy of “blaming the victim” continues in this play, and Venus is blamed for displaying her body to the people, but the people who look, ogle, and poke at her, and the persons who arrange for the display, escape the accusations.

Venus is described thus by a Chorus Member: “Thuh gals got bottoms like hot air balloons./Bottoms and bottoms and bottoms pilin up like/ Like 2 mountains. Magnificent. And endless./ An ass to write home about” (7-8). The White audience associates the poor Black woman with meanness and animality. The Overture introduces the nature of Venus’s exploitation and the public’s view of her. People are voyeuristic; out of their free will, they pay to see her, yet blame her for being “a filthy slut” (8). Mother Showman and the Chorus represent the White capitalists who make money out of a Black body with an anomaly. The diseased Black female body is described in terms of its sexual appeal to its spectators. The body of Venus is deprived of human value; she is treated like an animal, displayed, denied clothing, and caged, but moral and Christian standards judge her character as laden with sin and moral depravity.

Venus is introduced as The Girl, working in the house of White settlers in South Africa. The Brother of The Man expects financial support from The Man to start a new business. He has come up with the idea of a freak show with “The African Dancing Princess”, and The Man expresses concern over the availability of a girl. The Brother responds that the availability of a woman’s body is the easiest part of the venture. He

adds, "There is a street over there lined with Freak Acts/ but not many dark ones, that is how we will cash in" (12). The poor Black female body is free to be exploited by any rich White male member of society. The Brother expresses his sense of wonder to see Little Sarah, Venus, with whom he was much obsessed twelve years ago, so grown up. The Man replies, "As they all do. Big Bottomed Girls. That is their breed" (13). The animal imagery is employed throughout the play to describe Venus's various characteristics. Seeing her dance, The Brother says, "The Brits will eat it up. / Oh, she would make a splendid freak" (14). The Black woman is considered an exotic object, a freak, a curiosity, and a commodity to be consumed by the White male customers.

The Girl is lured into going to England. She is sexually exploited by The Brother, in the name of love, after she arrives in England. She keeps repeating, "It is dark in here" (23). Parks rewrites the notion of darkness by associating it with the imperialist nation that described Africa as the Dark Continent. A sharp, stinging irony is found in the Girl's request for a new dress. Venus is unaware that she will soon be deprived of the only dress that she wears, as The Brother sells her to Mother Showman, who displays her naked, as Venus and the Ninth Wonder, in her freak show. The descriptions of the wonders present derogatory views on the Africans and taunt the audience about the racist tendencies that are prevalent in American society.

Venus is presented to the audience for the first time by the Mother-Showman: "The Venus Hottentot/ She bottoms at the bottom of the ladder/ But truly, folks, before she showed up our little show was in the red/, But her big bottoms friends will surely put us safely in the black!" (35). She also says, "What a bucket! What a bum! What a spanker!" (45). She also describes her in a much abusive way, "The only living creature of her kind in the world/ Stepsister monkey to the great venal/ love/ goddess" (35). Footnote#3 of the play, from Robert Chambers' *Book of Days*, describes Venus, "With an intensely ugly figure, distorted beyond all European notions of beauty" (36).

The Negro Resurrectionist reads from a newspaper advertisement in Footnote#4, "From Daniel Lysons *Collectanea: A Collection of Advertisements and Paragraphs from the Newspapers Relating to Various Subjects* (London, 1809): Parties of 12 and upwards, may be accommodated with a Private Exhibition of the Hottentot ... between 7 and 8 o'clock in the evening" (44). Another advertisement states, "The Hottentot may also be viewed by single parties with no advance notice from 10 in the morning until 10 in the evening. Mondays through Saturdays. No advance notice is necessary... A woman will attend (if required)" (44). These newspaper extracts reveal the ultimate ugliness of the exploitation of Venus. Venus is not accorded the status of a woman, and the role of the attending woman is not to avoid the embarrassment of Venus, but that of the onlookers.

The Mother-Showman employs psychological manipulation of the crowd by asking them to “feel like a King!” (45) on seeing Venus. The inferior status accorded to the poor Black woman assigns a superior role even to the poor Whites of the society. The Mother-Showman kicks Venus till she goes out of breath, and gives a humiliating account of the behaviour of the Hottentot race, “Thuh kicks is native for he Hottentots./ ... Uh whole language of kicks/ very sophisticated/ for them of course” (46). The White nation that does not have a traditional and mythical past demeans a nation that was the site of great civilizations in the past.

The African Hottentots are presented as uncultured, uncivilised people with no proper language structure for communication. Their homes are described as “hot”, referring to the climate of the geographical region and also to the sexuality of the Hottentots. The demeaning White perspective of the language of the Hottentots gets expressed in another context, when the Uncle and the Would-be Bride in *For the Love of Venus*, “click and cluck at each other” (133) in order to communicate. The Uncle states, “Her hometown lingos uh strange one” (133), referring to the language of the African Community as primitive and wild.

The Mother-Showman earns a lot by exhibiting the naked Venus in a cage, yet she economically exploits Venus. Venus expresses her opposition to the exploitation and demands a fair share of money, and Mother-Showman gives expression to the plight of the poor Black women: “They do not let your kind run loose in the streets/ much less set up their own stage” (56). Venus’ desire to lead an independent life is thus discouraged, as the Blacks were denied any chance of enjoying financial independence and economic self-reliance. The Mother-Showman also threatens Venus: “Dont push me, Sweetie/ Next door a smoky pub/ full of drunken men./ I just may invite them in/ one at a time/ and let them fuck yr brains out” (56), and Venus’ reply, “They do it anyway” (56) expresses the ultimate exploitation of the Black woman by the White society. A poor Black woman is exploited even by the poor Whites who are regular visitors to a cheap, smoky pub.

The White society gains much by its exploitation of the Black body; the Mother-Showman receives financial gain; the spectators derive pleasure as their voyeuristic impulses are satisfied. “The things they noticed were quite various/ but no one ever noticed that her face was streamed with tears” (47). The Black woman has accepted her exploitation as a path to earn money and gain social status, yet she feels ashamed at the way she is treated, and mourns the absence of dignity and love in her life. Venus expresses her desire to prove her intelligence to the crowd. However, her suggestions are neglected by the Mother-Showman, who says, “Y r a Negro native with a most remarkable spanker./That is what they pay for./ Their eyes are hot for yr tot-tot./There is the poetry” (51). The Whites consider the Black body as a site of sensual and sexual pleasure, and to them, it can never be a site of intelligence.

Venus's status as a commodity is reiterated throughout the play as she is repeatedly bought and sold by different characters. The Black female body is objectified for the White consumers, and her race, class, and gender interlock inseparably in bringing about her oppression. Baron Docteur buys her from Mother-Showman and persuades her to move with him to France, promising her a clean room, mixing with his associates, and moving in a better circle. The Baron Docteur is an anatomist, trying to advance his career by performing an anatomy on a Hottentot woman and publishing the findings, adding to the store of pseudo-scientific knowledge on the inferiority and subhuman nature of the Black race, and thus proving the superiority of the White race. Venus, ignorant of the dark motives of the Baron Docteur, falls in love with him, and the body of Venus is exploited clinically and sexually by the Baron Docteur. He compels her twice to undergo an abortion.

Venus appears to have a chance to choose, but in reality, she is not allowed to make any choice. The Brother does not give her a choice when he asks her if she wants to go with him to England. He already made the decision, and Venus has to go with it. The Baron Docteur appears to ask for her permission to accompany him to Paris, but he has already purchased her from the Mother-Showman, and this leaves her with no choice. The Docteur also makes her choose to have an abortion. The Whites always suppress the intelligence of Venus around her. Mother-Showman does not want her to reveal to anyone her ability to count. When she offers to recite some poems to the audience, Mother-Showman denies her permission to do so, as she thinks the White crowd is interested only in the body and not the brain of Venus. The Anatomists marvel at Venus' ability to pick up French fast, and the Baron Docteur states that she is a "glorious exception" (112), for the race she belongs to is believed to be incapable of using the intellect.

The Baron Docteur's report on the physical characteristics of Venus establishes her otherness. Scientific interest in Saartjie Baartman was due to the difference in her genitalia. Schiebinger states, "Nothing excites these (scientists) more than the elongation of the labia minora ... among the Hottentot. This 'Hottentot apron' became the subject of countless books and articles, and much prurient popular and scientific speculation" (10). The Baron Docteur's report also describes Venus' breasts, ears, and movements; the way she pushes her lips is compared to that of a monkey. Londa Schielbinger says, "Baartman's history is characterized by radical misreadings of the human body that scholars have described as scientific racism and scientific sexism". Parks presents "the Black body, specifically the Black female body, as other and nonnormative. Caricatured and stereotyped, this staged body resembles historically racist images of the Black female as the mammy, Jezebel, and breeder woman. However, she also positions this body as the protagonist ... and, in so doing, urges the audience to question the validity of these stereotypes" (Young 46).

Venus is ignorant of the systematic and structuralized racism, classism, and sexism “mapped across the Black female body” (Young 44). She may have refused to accompany *The Brother* to England. However, the other options she has in her life are not better, in any way, than the one she has chosen. Her presence in the intersection of race, class, and gender destines her to be subjugated and oppressed throughout her life. The men in the play can survive only by the racial, sexual, and economic exploitation of Venus. Venus satisfies the voyeuristic needs of the people of her period; she struggles to survive the ruthless racial, economic, and sexual exploitation and abuse, but fails in her attempt owing to the systematic intersection of race, class, and gender imperial power structures.

Conclusion

An intersectional analysis of *Venus* brings out the institutionalised oppression of women of colour by means of racism, classism, sexism, pseudo-science, and colonialism. It establishes the lack of agency, and quite ironically, the complicity of the protagonist in her oppression, and emphasises a need to rewrite history from a postcolonial and Black Feminist perspective. It also enables a critical study of the commodification of the Black female body and scientific misogyny that ensures the permanency of the intersectional oppression of women of colour through the interlocking categories of race, class, and gender.

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